

**THE OPTIMAL SERVICE AREA OF THE LOGISTICS CENTER OF
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Annotation: In this article, the establishment of an optimal service area for logistics centers is examined, emphasizing the adherence to established time delivery norms for diverse cargoes. The article strongly supports a model grounded in a time function as a fundamental approach for constructing a critical isochrone, thereby ensuring the reliable fulfillment of orders within predetermined time standards. This model takes into account various factors that significantly influence the objective function, including the intensity of requests, time intervals between shipments, the average number of orders per vehicle, vehicle speed, route characteristics, trajectory of consumer visits, and time overhead for operational processes. By integrating these factors, the proposed model aims to provide a comprehensive framework for logistics center enterprises to effectively manage and optimize their service areas while meeting the critical requirements of timely order delivery.

Keywords: logistic centers, service area, delivery route, transport vehicles.

It is widely recognized that ensuring high-quality service parameters significantly enhances the competitiveness of an enterprise. One of the key indicators of service quality is the minimization of the time period from the customer's order placement to the delivery to the consumer.

For these purposes, enterprise logistic centers are typically in operation, such as post offices, express delivery service branches, order pickup points for network hypermarkets, internet stores, and other enterprises in wholesale and retail trade.

For effective regional coverage by logistic centers, a crucial task is determining the optimal service area of the center. In [1], Yu. M. Nerush justified a methodology for determining the rational radius of a firm's operational zone based on marginal and average costs. The radii obtained in this way for the service areas of micrologistics centers are not directly related to order fulfillment times and cannot guarantee delivery within the established time norm. In [2], Pirat suggested determining the attraction of territorial points to a particular service center using lines of equal distance, while in [3], Gerhard Pottgoff proposed using isochrones. Limiting the territory in this way is valid in calculations for radial straight routes from the center, possibly with adjustments for the known curvature of traffic routes.

At the same time, most logistics centers consolidate shipments of small-scale cargo, ensuring the rational use of the carrying capacity and load capacity of transport vehicles. The mandatory processing of consolidated cargo, formed by a sequence of consumer requests, imposes certain features on the model of the optimal service area of the enterprise's logistics center.

We believe that it is expedient to base such a model on a time function depending on the considered factors, which will be presented below. In this case, the objective function, expressed as a time function, should strive to approach the order fulfillment time norm from below. As a result, it will be possible to construct a critical isochrone limiting the area of guaranteed order fulfillment within the established time norm.

It is advisable to include the following factors in the objective function, affecting order execution time:

- intensity of requests received or average intervals between them, if the formation of the shipment occurs faster than the time intervals between applications. Or the time intervals between the formation of shipments for

orders, if the time intervals between orders

less than the duration of the order shipment;

- the average number of orders delivered by one vehicle.

In addition, when forming the dependence of the objective function, it is necessary to take into account the average speed of the vehicle, the curvilinearity of the route and its length, the trajectory of the visit consumers, time overhead for freight and commercial operations.

An essential consideration pertains to the number of orders fulfilled by a single transport vehicle, as it is evident that varying quantities of orders on a single transport vehicle will constrain different service areas with the same critical isochrone. The greater the number of orders executed by a single transport vehicle, the narrower the geographical coverage of the service area constrained by the critical isochrone. For the purpose of simplifying the foundational model, it is noteworthy that each order is unique and designated for a single customer pickup point. Subsequently, the foundational model can be refined by lifting this constraint.

Thus, it will be possible to address two optimization tasks – constructing the optimal zone for a known quantity of orders serviced by a single transport vehicle or determining the optimal number of orders fulfilled by a single transport vehicle for a known service area. The most challenging aspect lies in assessing the true trajectory of the vehicle from the logistics center and the sequence of visits to customer pickup points for completed orders.

Although, it is evident that the maximum feasible temporal length of the rational route circumnavigation trajectory possesses the following properties:

- all customer pickup points lie on the critical isochrone line and are maximally temporally spaced apart during transit between them.
- the circumnavigation of customer pickup points is carried out sequentially from the center to one of the points and subsequently to the next nearest point in terms of transit time, until all customer points have been visited exhaustively.

The illustration depicts an exemplary circumnavigation route trajectory for 3 and 4 customer pickup points.

Pic. Rational circumnavigation route trajectories with maximum temporal mileage are presented on the left for 3 customer pickup points (requests) and on the right for 4: S_0 – micrologistics center; $M_1...M_4$ – customer pickup points for order reception; d – circumnavigation route trajectory; m – isochrone; v – missing side of the regular polygon figure.

Based on the aforementioned, it follows that within a specific isochrone, the trajectory with the maximum transit time for n points ensures that any other trajectory, under any other arrangement of the same number of points, will have a demonstrably shorter transit time. Therefore, if the conditions for the delivery time norm to the final point are satisfied along this critical trajectory, consequently, the conditions for the delivery time norm will be satisfied for all other trajectories within the isochrone zone for which the critical trajectory is formed.

Knowing the expression for the perimeter of a regular figure in terms of the radius of the circumscribed circle makes it easy to calculate the length of the trajectory in time units for an isochrone of a specific radius and number of points.

$$t_{ct} = t_r \left(1 + 2n - 1 \sin \frac{\pi}{n} \right)$$

where t_{ct} - is the length of the critical trajectory in time units; t_r - is the length of the isochrone radius in time units; and n - is the number of orders (customer pickup points).

At the same time, there is a constraint:

$$nI + t_{cc} + t_{ct} \leq t_{stan}$$

where I – the interval between requests or the duration of processing a request in a micro-logistics center in units of time (a large value is accepted); t_{cc} – the time for the execution of cargo and commercial operations at the customer service point; t_{stan} – the standard time for fulfilling an order from the moment of the customer's request to the issuance of the completed order.

Using the expressions provided above, it is possible to calculate the isochrone radius for the maximum possible service area under t_{stan} and n given conditions:

$$t_r = \frac{t_{stan} - nI + t_{cc}}{1 + 2n - 1 \sin \frac{\pi}{n}}$$

In the end, the radius of the service area in kilometers will be expressed by the following formula:

$$R = \frac{V t_{stan} - nI + t_{cc}}{K_{cf} (1 + 2n - 1 \sin \frac{\pi}{n})}$$

where V is the average speed of the vehicle in kilometers per hour; and K_{cf} is the curvature factor, taking into account deviations of the route from a straight line on the terrain.

The value K_{cf} is greater than 1. In the conditions of city blocks of regular shape (all intersections of blocks at a right angle) [4], the value is equal to the ratio of the Manhattan distance to the Euclidean distance minus 1.414.

In cities located in mountainous terrain with intersecting rivers, the value of K_{cf} increases. However, when planning service areas with micro-logistics centers, it is advisable to use these natural obstacles as zone boundaries. This allows maintaining uniformity in the value of K_{cf} within the zone.

As seen from the calculations, the requirements for the unconditional fulfillment of an order within the established time norm impose strict constraints on the service area radius. In practice, by allowing risks of order fulfillment beyond the time norm, it is possible to establish radii of service areas corresponding to 5%, 10%, or any other risk norm. To do this, one should consider the service area with a guaranteed order fulfillment time as a proportion of the area (e.g., 95% for a 5% risk or 90% for a 10% risk) of the unknown 100% coverage zone.

The new radii of zones can be determined based on the dependency:

$$R_z = \frac{R^2}{1 - z} ,$$

where R_z - the radius of the optimal service area with z - the risk norm of order fulfillment in the established standard time; z - the risk norm of order fulfillment in the established standard time, expressed as a fraction of the unit.

Thus, by establishing the execution time standard, the number of orders in a consolidated cargo on a single transport vehicle can be used to find the radius of the optimal service area with a guaranteed order execution time. Operating with risks allows for an increase in the coverage radius of the optimal zone.

The solution to this problem will result in determining the required number of transport vehicles for the guaranteed service of the number of requests in the service area and the necessary number of micro-logistics centers and their locations for the guaranteed service of the region's consumers within the established order execution time standard.

References

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